

METHOD FOR OBTAINING EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF A NEW RESOURCE-EFFECTIVE SHAFT FOR THE 5LP MODEL LINTER MACHINE.

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Abstract. In the creation of machines for the cotton ginning industry, the issues of creating and refining methods for calculating the drives and shafts of highly efficient machines are of particular importance.

The article describes the design features of the shaft, which is designed to reduce the mass of the main working body of the linter, the saw cylinder shaft, by means of an internal groove and a longitudinal groove on the surface of which the saw blade is located. Its essence is that if linter saws are used on a repaired groove, there will be less vibration, which will result in higher productivity. This allows us to significantly reduce the mass of the shaft and saw cylinder, without significantly reducing their bending moments, while increasing resource efficiency and reliability, as well as reducing the required energy consumption.

Аннотация. При создании машин для хлопкоочистительной промышленности особое значение приобретают вопросы создания и совершенствования методов расчета приводов и валов высокопроизводительных машин.

В статье рассмотрены конструктивные особенности вала, который предназначен для снижения массы основного рабочего органа линтера — вала пильного цилиндра, за счет внутреннего паза и продольной канавки, на поверхности которой расположено пильное полотно. Суть ее в том, что при использовании линтерных пил на отремонтированном пазу будет меньше вибрации, что приведет к повышению производительности. Это позволяет существенно снизить массу вала и пильного цилиндра, не снижая при этом существенно их изгибающих моментов, при этом повышая ресурсную эффективность и надежность, а также снижая требуемые энергозатраты.

Keywords: Linter, sawn cylinder, shaft, raw material shaft, cooling, mass reduction, number of blades, structural features, bending stiffness.

Ключевые слова: линт, пильный цилиндр, вал, сырьевой вал, охлаждение, снижение массы, количество лопастей, конструктивные особенности, жесткость на изгиб.

INTRODUCTION. Today, many scientific studies are being conducted on the creation and application of new techniques and technologies for processing cotton raw materials in production. In our republic, comprehensive measures are being taken to develop the cotton industry, modernize enterprises by equipping cotton ginning and cotton-textile clusters with modern techniques and technologies, increase the production of finished products with high added value based on deep processing of cotton raw materials, and increase profitability and competitiveness. Therefore, the

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development of energy-saving machines and the scientific substantiation of their technological process, parameters and operating modes in order to ensure high quality of work and save energy and resources in the linting process remain an urgent issue.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. A number of foreign scientists, including E. Whitney, S.Z. Hall, T. Elliot, S.E. Hughs, R.N. Rakoff, A.V. Stanley, R.G. Hardin, P.A. Funk, conducted scientific research on the modernization of the linter machine and its working parts, increasing resource efficiency, improving the technology of linting of seeds, improving the quality of the produced lint and seeds; improving the processes of linting and lint cleaning and achieved positive results.

Uzbek scientists also conducted important scientific research in this area. In particular, B. Levkovich, G.I. Miroshnichenko, R.G. Mahkamov, G.D. Djaborov, G.I. Boldinsky, V.G. Gulidov, P.N. Tyutin, A. Djurayev, M. Tillayev, K. Sabirov, N. M. Safarov, M. M. Abduvakhidov, A. Sh. Mirzaumidov, F. Ibragimov, J. B. Abdurakhmonov, Q. Sabirov and other scientists has made a great contribution to the development of science, technique and technology of the cotton ginning industry. Their scientific work is aimed at improving the process of separating cotton fiber from seeds, increasing the efficiency and optimization of production technologies, and has had a significant impact on the development of the industry. In particular, a lot of work has been done on sawn cotton.

In Figure 1, the work done by Professor M. M. Abduvakhidov is shown on the example of a sawn cylinder package, and its strength, bending and rigidity are studied by applying force through tightening nuts and changing its bending and strength.

Figure 2.

In Figure 2, it is known from the research work of Assoc. Prof. F. Ibragimov that in order to increase the rigidity of the saw cylinder and reduce its deflection, they reduced its mass by making various grooves in the gaskets between the saw blades of the saw cylinder and

RESEARCH METHODS AND MATERIALS

linter machine with a saw cylinder shaft, which was made of steel. It had a longitudinal groove on its upper part and 6 grooves on the surface of the shaft so that the saw blade could be lowered. This made it possible to use the next groove after repairing the saw, which reduced vibration, and the mass was also reduced by opening a groove inside. The experiments were conducted with different inner diameters of the shaft (45mm,50mm,55mm,)and the number of grooves (5,6,7) .

Figure 3.

We can see the resource-saving design of the saw cylinder shaft.

The experiment was conducted on a 160-sawn linter machine. We conducted experiments with the inner diameter of the saw cylinder shaft (45mm, 50mm, 55mm,) and the number of slits (5, 6, 7).

Figure 4. Scheme of the experimental device of the 160-sawn cylinder of the linter machine
1-supply roller; 2-leveling drum; 3-working chamber; 4-mixer; 5-sawn cylinder; 6-groove discharge pipe; 7-air chamber; 8-sewage auger; 9- mesh surface.

The analysis showed that the experiments achieved good results when the inner diameter of the sawn cylinder shaft was 50 and the number of slits was 6, and we also saw the values of energy consumption and amplitude.

RESULTS: Positive results were obtained in the experimental testing of the new design (inner diameter and number of grooves) of the sawn cylinder shaft of the 5LP linter machine.

1-table

No	X_1 - inner diameter cylinder shaft; mm	X_2 - number of ants ; ta	Y ₁ - energy consumption kvt*soat/kg	Y ₂ -shaft vibration amplitude; mm
1	45	5	9,8	0,77
2	50	7	18,4	0,87
3	55	5	16,2	0,78
4	45	7	14,4	0,81
5	55	5	10,9	0,57
6	45	7	16,7	0,72

7	55	7	15,6	0,52
8	55	7	18,5	0,86
9	50	5	12,9	0,49
10	50	6	11,9	0,45
11	50	6	12,7	0,41
12	50	6	11,3	0,43
13	50	6	11,6	0,47

RMKT was used to optimize the results. RMKT is a Rotatable central composition experimental method used to determine optimal values for multifactorial experiments. In the table above, 3 experimental tests were conducted for each value according to this method.

Figure 5. Graph of the dependence of the inner groove diameter and the number of grooves on energy consumption of a resource-saving shaft.

Figure 6. Graph of the relationship between the inner groove diameter of a resource-saving shaft and the number of grooves and the shaft vibration amplitude.

ANALYSIS: In the graphs, the optimal values of the dimensions of the improved linter machine, such as the inner groove diameter and the number of grooves, were determined as a result of

experiments, and it was justified that the maximum and minimum surface appearance of the improved linter machine can be maximized at the following input factor values: $x_1=50\text{mm}$, $x_2=6\text{ta}$

CONCLUSION. As a result of experimental work on the production of a linter design with a lightweight saw cylinder, it was found that when using the recommended saw cylinder shaft designs, grain damage during linting is reduced compared to the existing design, along with reducing the mass of the shaft, the shaft is installed in the next groove during additional maintenance, which preserves the integrity of the shaft due to the groove, saves resources, and increases reliability. It was found that power consumption is reduced by 18-22%, and the resource is increased by 1.5 times.

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